
Advances in MOFs and their derivatives for non-noble metal electrocatalysts in water splitting

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Abstract

Green hydrogen is produced by water electrolysis using renewable energy sources. For green hydrogen to become cost-effective in front of hydrogen production from fossil fuels, highly active, efficient, and durable electrocatalysts based on abundant and low-cost elements need to be developed. Great efforts have been invested in designing and engineering water-splitting electrocatalysts with optimized compositions and architecture. In this last direction, metal-organic framework (MOF) compounds have received particular attention due to their high specific surface area (SSA), large pore volume, and excellent chemical stability. This work provides an overview of the latest progress in the design, engineering, and application of MOFs and their derivatives as electrocatalysts in water splitting. It further discusses the challenges encountered and the new research directions and application prospects. First, the characteristics and advantages of MOF electrocatalysts and the main mechanism of water electrolysis are introduced. Next, the research progress on the application of MOFs and their derivatives in water electrolysis is reviewed, with special emphasis on the preparation,

modification, and catalytic activity of the catalysts. Finally, the current challenges and future development prospects of MOFs as water-splitting electrocatalysts are discussed. Overall, this review aims to provide new insights into the design and synthesis principles of MOF materials, promoting their practical application in water splitting, and further broadening their future uses.

Keywords: water splitting; electrolysis, electrocatalysis; metal-organic framework; MOF-derivative, hydrogen, hydrogen evolution reaction, oxygen evolution reaction.

1. Introduction

The electrolysis of water requires the use of electrocatalysts able to reduce the reaction energy barrier, accelerate the reaction process, and improve its energy conversion efficiency.¹ Water-splitting electrocatalysts should: (i) provide high current densities at low overpotentials; (ii) be highly stable under operation conditions; (iii) be based on inexpensive, non-toxic, and abundantly available raw materials; and (iv) be produced by high throughput, high yield, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable approaches.

The electrolysis of water involves two half-reactions, the cathodic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and the anodic oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Currently, commercial electrolysis systems use Pt-based catalysts for the HER,^{2,3} and Ir, Ru, and their oxides for the OER.^{4,5} The limited supply and high cost of such precious metals limit the cost-effectiveness of electrolyzers and thus the large-scale production of molecular hydrogen from water.⁶ Therefore, for the commercialization of a water-splitting technology able to compete with hydrogen production from fossil fuels, it is critical to develop high-activity and stable non-noble metal catalysts.^{7,8} In this direction, while some abundant transition metals show strong redox activities and hence potential as electrocatalysts for water splitting their activity and stability need to be further enhanced through rational engineering of their electronic properties and their architecture.

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are a class of porous material composed of metal centers and organic ligands, which offer outstanding tunability and a wide range of applications.^{9,10} Among their multiple uses, MOFs show particular potential in the field of electrocatalysis,¹¹⁻¹³ where they offer: (1) Large specific surface area (SSA) and highly ordered and widely adjustable porous structure. Single or mixed pore structures with a variety of pore sizes from micropores to mesoporous can be obtained through the selection of organic ligands and synthetic conditions. These characteristics maximize the dispersion of active components, provide a large number of active sites for electrocatalytic reactions, and facilitate the proton transfer process of electrocatalytic reactions; (2) Outstanding degree of functionalization and modification, and the related high capacity to be combined with other functional substances to improve electrocatalytic performance; (3) Abundant metal centers as active sites for electrocatalytic reactions. Besides as a precursor, the uniform distribution of metal centers within MOFs translates into MOF-derived materials that maintain an excellent metal dispersion even in the form of single atoms, thus improving the metal utilization rate. In addition, during the synthesis process, the organic ligand can be used to introduce the required heteroatoms to form heteroatomic functional groups in the derivatives, or proper anions to transform the metal centers into metallic compounds in a subsequent treatment.¹⁴

In this review, the latest research progress in the development and use of MOF and MOF-derived materials in electrocatalytic water splitting is discussed (**Scheme 1**). First, we overview the HER and OER mechanisms. Then, the synthesis strategy, catalytic activity, identification of active sites, and modification of MOF electrocatalysts are reviewed. Finally, the current challenges, current prospects, and future opportunities of MOF electrocatalysts are discussed.

Scheme 1. Overview of MOFs and their derivatives (LDH = layered double hydroxide; TMO = transition metal oxide; TMN = transition metal nitride; TMC = transition metal carbide; TMS = transition metal sulfide; TMP = transition metal phosphide) as electrocatalysts in water splitting.

2. Electrocatalytic mechanisms

The electrocatalytic water splitting involves two half-reactions, the cathodic HER and the anodic OER (Fig. 1).^{15,16} Considering the different electrolytes, they can be expressed as follows.

Acidic electrolyte:

Alkaline electrolyte:

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a water-splitting electrolyzer.

HER is a two-electron transfer process that in acidic media involves two steps:¹⁷ First, an electron combines with a proton on the electrode surface to produce an adsorbed H* (Volmer step, equation (6)). Subsequently, the adsorbed H* combines with a second proton in solution (Heyrovsky process, equation (7)) or another adsorbed hydrogen (Tafel step, equation (8)) to produce H₂. When a relatively small amount of H* is formed on the catalyst surface, the Volmer-Heyrovsky steps occur successively (right route in **Fig. 2a, b**). When enough H* is generated on the catalyst, the Volmer-Tafel steps become more effective (left route in **Fig. 2a, b**).

The Gibbs free energy of H* adsorption (ΔG_{H^*}) on the catalyst surface greatly affects the HER efficiency, with materials providing ΔG_{H^*} values close to zero being regarded as the most effective HER electrocatalysts. Under alkaline conditions, H* is generated in the hydrolysis step ($\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{e}^- + \text{M} \rightarrow \text{MH}^* + \text{OH}^-$), thus the HER activity is affected by both the hydrolysis step and ΔG_{H^*} .

The OER mechanisms are shown in **Fig. 2c, d**.^{18,19} Under alkaline conditions, two OER pathways are possible. A possible path follows reactions (9), (10), and (11). OH⁻ is adsorbed on the surface of the catalyst donating an e⁻ to form OH*. The OH* combines with another OH⁻, donating a second e⁻ and an H⁺ that releases an H₂O and

leaves an adsorbed O^* . Then, two adsorbed O^* form O_2 . The other path follows the sequence of reactions (9), (10), (12), and (13), where the adsorbed O^* generated in (10) combines with an OH^- losing a third e^- to form OOH^* . This OOH^* donates a fourth electron to form O_2 .

The surface metal cations (M) are generally considered the OER active sites, and the strength of the M–O bonds that form the intermediates (M–O, M–OH, and M–OOH) plays a key role in the electrocatalytic activity. Similar to the adsorption of H^* in HER, during the OER, a too strong M–O bond hinders the O_2 desorption, while a too weak M–O bond prevents the bonding of intermediates on the surface of the anode material.

Figure 2. Schematic pathways for (a, b) HER and (c, d) OER, under acidic (a, c) and alkaline (b, d) conditions.¹⁷⁻¹⁹

Theoretically, the voltage required for water splitting is 1.23 V. However, in

practical applications, significantly larger voltages, typically above 1.5 V, are required to initiate the reaction. Besides, due to the slow HER and OER kinetics, even higher overpotentials are needed to accelerate the reactions and run the process at sufficient hydrogen generation rates. To maximize the energy efficiency of the process, materials able to minimize the reaction energy barriers, offering high densities of reaction sites, and a proper architecture to allow effective transport of electrons, reactants, and products are required.

3. MOF-based electrocatalysts

As noted above, MOFs and MOF derivatives show great potential as electrocatalytic materials because they offer large metal site densities within a highly porous architecture characterized by a large surface area. Besides, all MOF parameters including the pore size, composition, and metal chemical environment and electronic states, can be precisely tuned to optimize performance. This last direction, the synthesis of new MOFs with rationally designed structures and properties, has been the main focus of a large part of the works in the field.

A variety of preparation methods are currently available for the synthesis of MOFs, including hydrothermal/solvothermal,²⁰⁻²² coprecipitation,²³ microwave-assisted,²⁴ spray drying,^{25,26} reflux,²⁷ and mechanochemical²⁸ approaches (**Fig. 3**). The diversity of synthesis methods allows producing a broader range of materials, which extends the palette of MOFs available for a variety of applications. Besides, each method offers different potential advantages in terms of processing costs, time, volume, yield, safety, etc. For example, compared with the traditional solvothermal method, microwave radiation directly heats the reactants, significantly lowering the reaction time and energy consumption. As another example, reaction systems working at atmospheric pressure are generally safer than those employing relatively high pressures.

Fig. 3 Scheme of the preparation of MOFs with different methodologies.

Although some pure MOF electrocatalysts display excellent catalytic activity, their active sites and catalytic mechanisms are still poorly understood. In addition, it is difficult for the electrolyte to enter the metal nodes inside the bulk MOFs, and the MOFs have poor conductivity, so the optimization of MOF catalysts still offers a large room for improvement.^{29,30}

3.1 Monometallic MOFs

During electrocatalysis, metal centers in MOFs with unsaturated coordination can effectively reduce steric hindrance, thus enhancing mass transfer, reducing electron conduction resistance, and improving affinity with reactants.³¹ Based on this, Yin et al.³² proposed a hydrothermal synthesis method to produce a Co-MOF presenting Co metal centers with unsaturated coordination (denoted as Co-BTC-IMI, **Fig. 4a**). Within this MOF, each Co ion is connected with just two deprotonated benzenecarboxylic acids. Compared with Co-BTC, with better coordination of cobalt nodes, the coordinatively unsaturated Co within Co-BTC-IMI shows less steric hindrance to molecular water and oxygen, and thus less resistance to electron transfer. Co-BTC-IMI was tested as OER electrocatalyst in O₂-saturated 0.1 KOH. It required only 1.59 V (vs. RHE) to reach a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² and showed a Tafel slope of 88 mV dec⁻¹, denoting a fast dynamic response (**Fig. 4b, c**). To have a deeper understanding of the catalytic

mechanism of OER, charge difference density analysis was performed on the Co centers and adjacent atoms, as shown in **Fig. 4d and e**. The cyan area denotes that electrons are lost and the yellow area is the area where electrons are gained. In Co-BTC-IMI and Co-BTC, the Co center usually loses electrons to neighboring O atoms as water molecules are adsorbed. According to Bader charge analysis, the Co center in Co-BTC-IMI loses 0.0768 electrons, while the Co center in Co-BTC loses only 0.0114 electrons. This higher valence metal, which is responsible for O-O double bond formation in the OER process, explains the better OER catalytic activity of Co-BTC-IMI compared with Co-BTC. This work demonstrated the possibility of directly applying pure-phase MOFs, i.e. unpyrolyzed, as electrocatalysts reaching highly competitive activities.

Figure 4. (a) Synthetic procedure and coordination environment of Co(II) in Co-BTC-IMI. (b) OER ring disk electrode (RDE) voltammograms of the studied samples at 1600 rpm in O₂-saturated 0.1 KOH. (c) OER Tafel curve of Co-BTC-IMI. (d, e) Charge difference density between Co centers and adjacent atoms in Co-BTC-IMI (d) and Co-BTC (e). The cyan areas indicate the areas losing electrons, and the yellow areas indicate gaining electrons.³²

Compared with one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) structures, three-dimensional (3D) flower-like structures can provide a larger accessible surface area, more exposed catalytic sites, lower mass transfer resistance, and higher electron

transport efficiency.^{33,34} Chao et al.³⁵ designed and obtained a series of MOFs with different morphologies using a one-pot solvothermal method. For example, F-Ni-MOFs (flower-like Ni-MOFs), F-Cu-MOFs (flower-like CuMOFs), Co-MOFs-NPs (Co-MOFs nanoplates) and Co-MOFs-MCs (Co-MOFs microcuboids) (**Fig. 5d-g**). F-Co-MOFs showed the highest activity and stability for OER and HER associated with an improved architecture, with many pores (**Fig. 5a-c**) that increase the surface area and provide open channels for the transfer of electrolyte ions and electrons (**Fig. 5h, i**).

Figure 5. FESEM images of F-Co-MOFs (a), F-Ni-MOFs (d), F-Cu-MOFs (e), Co-MOFs-NPs (f) and Co-MOFs-MCs (g). TEM images (b), N₂ sorption isotherm (c) of F-Co-MOFs. (h) OER polarization curves at 1600 rpm. (i) HER polarization curves at 1600 rpm.³⁵

3.2 Bimetallic MOFs

Compared with monometallic MOFs, bimetallic MOFs offer additional degrees of freedom for adjusting the active sites and can benefit from the synergistic effect between the two metals.^{36,37} For example, NiFe-MOFs, NiCo-MOFs, and CoFe-MOFs have attracted much attention as electrocatalysts for water splitting.^{38,39}

Fe-based MOFs have shown excellent stability in alkaline electrolytes due to the strong Fe-O coordination bond between the unsaturated metal cationic centers (Fe(III)) and -COOH groups of the organic ligand.⁴⁰⁻⁴² However, the use of pure MOFs as electrocatalysts, particularly Fe-based MOFs, is limited by their moderate conductivity and the challenges associated with facilitating electrolyte access to the metal nodes inside the MOF. Numerous works have shown that bimetallic MFe-MOF systems can increase electrical conductivity and decrease the Gibbs adsorption energy. In this direction, Chen et al.⁴³ synthesized a series of Fe-based bimetallic MOFs (MFe-BDC, M = Mg, Zn, Cd, BDC = 1,4-benzenedicarboxylate) by hydrothermal method. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis showed a strong electronic interaction between M and Fe atoms, which can effectively regulate the charge density of Fe (**Fig. 6a**). Electrochemical tests showed that CdFe-BDC provided the best OER, HER, and overall water splitting performance, with overpotentials of $\eta_{100} = 290$ mV, $\eta_{10} = 148$ mV, and $\eta_{10} = 1.63$ V, respectively (**Fig. 6b-d**). This excellent performance was rationalized using DFT calculations, which showed that the introduction of Cd can adjust the OH* and H* adsorption energies of CdFe-BDC, reduce the energy barrier of the rate-determining step, and improve the catalytic activity (**Fig. 6e, f**).

Figure 6. MFe-BDC analysis. (a) High-resolution XPS analyses of Fe 2p. LSV curves for OER (b), HER (c), and overall water splitting (d). Free energy profiles for the HER pathway (e) and the OER pathway (f).⁴³

3.3 Guest@MOFs composites

While MOFs offer stable porous structures, large surface area, and a high density of unsaturated metal sites, as noted above, their poor conductivity and low active site accessibility greatly hinder their practical application.^{44,45} To meet the strict requirements of practical electrocatalysis, besides optimizing the composition and architecture of MOFs, combining them with other functional materials to construct MOF-based composites is also an effective strategy.⁴⁶ The introduction of a second active substance on the surface of MOFs could theoretically improve the overall catalytic performance. However, building MOFs-based multiphase structures without sacrificing the inherent advantages of MOFs has proven extremely challenging. An effective strategy is the partial conversion of a sacrificial MOF preserving the MOF characteristics while introducing a second phase and ensuring the tightness of the two combinations. Normally, the introduced second phase plays a key catalytic role in guest@MOFs composites.

The interface engineering method provides a broad application prospect for the development of novel functional MOF catalysts. Recently, Luo et al.⁴⁷ reported a general gas phase method, which uses metal hydroxyl fluoride as a self-sacrificing template to grow ordered MOFs on conductive carbon cloth (CC), and then proceeded surface vulcanization with Na₂S to obtain the final catalyst Co₃S₄/EC-MOF (**Fig. 7a, b**). Compared with EC-Co(OH)F and EC-MOF, the electrocatalytic performance of the prepared Co₃S₄/EC-MOF hybrid was significantly improved, achieving high HER (84 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) and OER (226 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) performance (**Fig. 7c, e**). DFT calculations and further experiments showed that the electron transfer between Co₃S₄ species and MOF reduced the electron density of the Co *d*-band and optimized the Co adsorption performance (**Fig. 7d**).

In another study on the synthesis of guest@MOFs using MOFs as pre-catalyst, Lin et al.⁴⁸ prepared two kinds of Ni-based MOFs (Ni-BDC-1 and Ni-BDC-3) with different topology and morphology, and realized the activation of MOFs through electrochemical cyclic voltammetry (**Fig. 7f**). They found that dehydrated Ni-BDC-3

easily reconstruct into NiOOH (Ni-BDC-3R) during activation. Due to the weak hydrogen bonding between the interlayer coordination water molecules, the reconstruction of hydrated Ni-BDC-1 is inhibited, and a stable self-reconstructed MOF heterojunction (Ni-BDC-1R) is formed (Fig. 7g, h). The results showed that the OER activity of Ni-BDC-1R was significantly increased, and the overpotential at 10 mA cm^{-2} was only 225 mV (Fig. 7i). DFT calculations showed that a strong electrostatic field is formed between the internal MOF matrix and the surface-evolved NiOOH, which can effectively promote the redox of surface active Ni sites (Fig. 7g).

Figure 7. (a) Schematic illustration of the preparation procedure. (b) XRD patterns. (c,d) LSV curves for HER (c) and OER (d). (e) Calculated free energy diagram of the HER;⁴⁷ (f) Schematic illustration of the self-reconstruction of MOF heterojunction. (g,h) Raman spectroscopy (g) and PXRD results (h) of Ni-BDC-1, Ni-BDC-3, Ni-BDC-1R, and Ni-BDC-3R. (i) CV curves with a scan rate of 0.5 mV s^{-1} . (j) Calculated free energy diagrams of OER on Ni-BDC-1R and -3R in 1 M KOH.⁴⁸

3.4 MOFs@substrate composites

An extended strategy to improve the electrical conductivity and electrochemical activity of MOFs is combining them with high-conductivity materials (e.g. carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene, nickel foam, etc). MOFs and conductive substrates constitute MOFs@substrate composites where the conductive material contributes to the charge transport and MOFs are the main catalytically active substances. Again, the proper design and engineering of the interphase between the two materials are extremely challenging.^{49,50} Lin's group⁵¹ reported a series of MOFs composed of M_{12} ($M = \text{Zr}$ and Hf) secondary structural units and dicarboxylic acid ligands, which can meet many requirements as efficient electrocatalysts. These MOF nanosheets were only a few nanometers thick and had a short distance between ligands, so that MOF nanosheets could carry out efficient electron transfer, and they were also stable in aqueous solution. To obtain a synergistic effect between the catalytic active site of MOFs and the electrical conductivity of CNTs, Hf_{12} -porphyrin MOFs (Hf_{12} -CoDBP) were combined with CNTs through covalent bonding resulting in high-efficiency HER electrocatalysts (Hf_{12} -CoDBP/CNT). TEM images showed that the morphology of MOF nanoplates in the composites did not change during the composite formation (**Fig. 8a**). The covalent connection of Hf_{12} -porphyrin MOF nanosheets with conducting CNTs improved electrical conductivity and promoted the transfer of electrons from the electrode to the Co-porphyrin active sites, thus achieving efficient proton reduction via protonation of $\text{Co}^{\text{I}}\text{-H}$ intermediate (**Fig. 8b**). Hf_{12} -CoDBP/CNT exhibited significant HER activity in perchloric acid solution with $\text{pH} = 1$. When the current density reached 10 mA cm^{-2} , the overpotential was 650 mV (**Fig. 8c**).

It is generally difficult to improve one of the parameters without sacrificing other advantages of the catalyst. For example, to improve the electrical conductivity of MOFs, high-temperature pyrolysis strategies can be used, but this typically destroys the carefully designed metal active sites of MOFs,⁵² and hybrid modification methods with conductive carriers (conductive polymers, graphene, etc.) may block the intrinsic pore structure of MOFs.^{53,54} Besides, since most reported 2D MOFs are prepared in powder

form, some active sites may be blocked due to the stacking effect of nanosheets during electrode construction. Compared with powder electrocatalysts, thin film electrocatalysts grown or properly deposited on the conductive support provide a stronger bond and closer electrical contact with the electrode, improving charge and ion transfer during the reaction. Thus, they generally show higher durabilities. Therefore, the direct preparation of MOF nanoarrays on target substrates, such as CC or Ni foam,^{55,56} is a promising method to improve the catalytic performance of MOFs. Recently, Qi et al.⁵⁷ prepared CoNi-MOF nanoarrays on CC (CoNiBDC/CC) by a spray synthesis method at room temperature (**Fig. 8d**). The CC surface is completely and uniformly covered with an array of vertical nanosheets (**Fig. 8e**), which contribute to improving the access of active sites, the adhesion of electrocatalyst electrodes and the proton transfer of electrolytes and products. CoNiBDC/CC with a large external area showed an overpotential of 251 mV for OER, 135 mV for HER, and 1.625 V for overall water splitting at 10 mA cm^{-2} (**Fig. 8f-h**).

Figure 8. (a) TEM images of $\text{Hf}_{12}\text{-CoDBP/CNT}$. (b) Differential pulse voltammetry of $\text{Hf}_{12}\text{-CoDBP}$ in acetonitrile with (blue) and without (red) TFA. (c) CV curves in 0.1 M aqueous perchloric acid⁵¹; (d) Scheme of the preparation of CoNiBDC/CC using the spray method. (e) SEM images of

As noted above, pure MOFs have a large number of metal centers, but their nanoscale pore size limits the utilization of active sites becoming an additional key factor constraining their performance.⁵⁸⁻⁶² A strategy to overcome this limitation is to maximize the surface exposure of the active sites, i.e. minimize the inaccessible internal MOF structure, by producing ultrathin MOF nanosheets on a conductive support. In this direction, Zhao et al.⁶³ reported a one-step chemical deposition method based on the dissolution–crystallization mechanism, which realized the preparation of ultra-thin 2D NiFe-MOF arrays on different conductive substrate materials (**Fig. 9a**). This preparation method can adjust and optimize a variety of structural parameters of MOF materials. The material has multi-level pore structures, including the micropores of MOFs, the open pores of the 2D nanosheet in the array, and the large pores of the nickel foam substrate (**Fig. 9b**). Based on the ultrathin thickness, most of the active centers of 2D MOFs are exposed, and the electrical conductivity of the material is improved (**Fig. 9c, d**). The NiFe-MOF showed excellent electrocatalytic performance, with overpotentials of OER, HER, and overall water splitting of 240 mV, 134 mV, and 1.55 V, respectively, at 10 mA cm⁻² in 0.1 M KOH (**Fig. 9e-g**). Additional works on MOF-based electrocatalysts are listed in **Table 1**.

Figure 9. (a) Synthetic process of MOF nanosheet array. Morphological characterization of NiFe-MOF electrodes. (b) SEM images (scale bars, 1 μm). (c) TEM image (Scale bar, 100 nm). (d) EIS spectra of NiFe-MOF in comparison to its bulk and sheet. (e-g) Electrocatalytic properties of NiFe-MOF and other samples, LSV plots of OER (e), HER (f), and overall water splitting (g) ⁶³.

Table 1. Summary of some MOF-based electrocatalysts for water splitting

Electrocatalyst	Electrolyte	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Overpotential (mV)	Reference
Hf ₁₂ -CoDBP /CNT	pH = 1	10	HER 650	51
CoNiBDC/CC	1 M KOH	10	HER 135	57
			OER 251	
Fe@Co-MOFs	1 M KOH	10	HER 150	64
		50	OER 248	
Co/Cu-MOF	1 M KOH	10	HER 391	65
		10	OER 380	
NiFe-MOF	1 M KOH	10	OER 168	66
NiFe-MOF-74	1 M KOH	10	HER 168	67
			OER 208	
(GO 8 wt%) Cu-MOF	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	30	HER 209	68

NiFe(dobpdc)	1 M KOH	10	HER 113	69
			OER 207	
	1 M KOH	100	HER 170	69
			OER 251	
MFN-MOFs/NF	1 M KOH	10	HER 79	70
		500	HER 234	
		50	OER 235	
		500	OER 294	
F-Co-MOFs	1 M KOH		HER 420	35
			OER 380	
Ni/Co/Fe-MOF	0.1 M KOH	10	HER 270	71
			OER 320	
MOF CoFeP	1 M KOH	50	HER 200	72
			OER 310	
CdFe-BDC	1 M KOH	10	HER 148	43
		100	OER 290	
NiYCe-MOF/NF	1 M KOH	10	HER 136	73
			OER 245	
CoNi-MOFs-DBD	1 M KOH	10	HER 203	74
		40	OER 168	

4. MOF-derived electrocatalysts

As noted above, MOFs offer a high density of metal sites, high porosities, and surface areas, and extreme tunability, but they generally lack enough electrical conductivities, solvent accessibility to the internal metal sites, and electrolyte and electrocatalytic stability, especially in alkaline solutions.^{75,76} To overcome their limitations, MOFs are often used as sacrificial templates to produce derivative materials that ideally conserve the large density of dispersed metal sites, large porosities, and

surface areas, but present improved electrical conductivity, accessibility, and stability under the relatively harsh electrolysis working environments.⁷⁷ The main challenge in the production of such MOF derivatives is to maintain a proper level of control over the final material properties.

4.1 MOF-derived metal-free carbon

Carbon-based catalysts have long been showing promising applications in HER electrocatalysis due to their excellent electronic conductivity, chemical and thermal stability, and environmental sustainability.⁷⁸ At the same time, it is found that the doping of heteroatoms (N, O, P, and S) and the introduction of functional groups can effectively regulate the electronic structure of carbon materials, greatly improving their catalytic performance^{79,80}. However, precisely controlling the uniform distribution of doping elements remains rather challenging.⁸¹

In recent years, there has been increasing interest in using MOFs as a precursor to prepare doped carbon materials with tuned properties. The organic parts in MOFs can be converted into a highly conductive carbon matrix through pyrolysis. At the same time, the heteroatoms in the precursor MOF can be uniformly distributed in the pyrolytic carbon materials as catalytic active sites.^{82,83} In addition, pores and pathways to the active site can be created through carbon/thermal reduction and evaporation of low-boiling metals (such as Zn) adjacent to heteroatoms. Qian et al.⁸⁴ prepared porous B-N dual-doped carbon materials through pyrolysis of Zn-MOFs, effectively improving the OER catalytic activity. N and B co-doping makes the surrounding carbon atoms positively charged, enhancing the electron transfer ability between the electrocatalyst and the reactant. By adjusting the pyrolysis atmosphere (H₂-Ar), the SSA of the pyrolysis product was further increased, and the catalytic activity for OER was greatly improved, achieving an overpotential of 1.55 V at 10 mA cm⁻² in 6 M KOH.

The electrocatalytic performance of pure carbon materials is moderate as the non-polar surface of carbon does not offer proper oxygen, proton, and hydroxide adsorption sites. Therefore, the type and level of heteroatom doping, as well as the composition of surface functional groups control a large part of the electrocatalytic performance of the

carbon material.⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷ For instance, the pyrolysis of ZIF-8 yields a high N-doped carbon material with a large SSA, and abundant micropores and mesopores.⁸⁸ In acidic solutions, cathodic polarization treatment (CPT) can adjust the composition of surface functional groups containing N and O in carbon materials without sacrificing their SSA and pore size distribution (**Fig. 10**). The optimized catalyst exhibited excellent HER and OER activities, showing overpotentials down to 155 mV for HER in acidic medium and 476 mV for OER in alkaline medium at a current density of 10 mA cm⁻².

Figure 10. (a) Schematic diagram of carbon electrocatalysts synthesized from ZIF-8. (b,c) Correlation between the abundance of several major functional groups and their electrocatalytic performances for HER (b) and OER (c).⁸⁸

4.2 MOF-derived layered double hydroxide

Some layered double hydroxides (LDHs) such as NiFe-LDH are one of the most appealing catalysts for alkaline electrolytic water OER because of their relatively low cost, abundant resources, and high intrinsic activity.⁸⁹⁻⁹³ LDHs can be also derived from MOF templates, showing excellent OER performance. However, the exposed active

sites are still limited, and the design of highly active MOF-derived LDH catalysts remains a challenge. Yeh et al.⁹⁴ reported the incorporation of novel heteroatom-doped graphene quantum dots (GQDs) into MOF-derived NiFe-LDH (**Fig. 11a**). XPS analysis showed that defects are produced due to the oxygen-rich functional groups and B, N doping, which leads to the formation of high valence Ni³⁺ and Fe³⁺. In addition, the defects act as nucleation and adsorption sites for Ni²⁺ and Fe³⁺ cations, which can enhance OER kinetics (**Fig. 11b, c**). The results of the analysis in **Fig. 11d** reflect the synergistic coupling effect of dual-doped B and N in the graphene, resulting in higher edges and defects and stronger coupling of Ni and Fe ions to the graphene. Due to the abundant active sites and synergistic effect, the designed B,N-GQDs/MOF-d-LDH exhibited superior catalytic performance in alkaline media, with an overpotential of only 251 mV at 100 mA cm⁻² (**Fig. 11e**).

Similarly, in another research effort, Liu et al.³⁹ constructed excellent LDH electrocatalysts by a cation regulation strategy (**Fig. 11f**). Due to the alkaline hydrolysis of Fe-modified Ni-MOFs with low stability, the prepared catalyst material was self-reconstructed under experimental conditions. The *in situ* self-reconstructed NiFe-LDH was the intrinsic catalytic active phase driving the OER process. A series of different catalysts (N-1, NF-5, NF-10, NF-20, and NF-50) were synthesized by adjusting the amount of Fe (0, 5, 10, 20, and 50 mM), in particular, samples containing Fe without Ni-MOF are labeled F-1. The ultrathin lamellar structure of Ni-MOFs-Fe was clearly observed in TEM images (**Fig. 11g**). The optimized catalyst NF-10 showed excellent OER electrocatalytic activity ($\eta_{50} = 280$ mV) due to the rich active center and bimetallic synergism (**Fig. 11h**). **Fig. 11i, j** demonstrate that there is a strong electronic interaction between Fe and Ni metals. The introduction of cation (Fe) in N-1 facilitates the formation of high valence metal active species in NF-LDH-based electrocatalysts and enhances the adsorption of reaction intermediates (*OH, *OOH, and *O).

Figure 11. (a) Schematic illustration of spontaneous transformation from heteroatom-doped GQDs/NiFe-MOF-74 to heteroatom-doped GQDs/MOF-derived-LDH. (b,c) High-resolution Ni 2p spectra (b) and Fe 2p (c) XPS spectra. (d) C K-edge soft-XAS spectra of GQDs/NiFe-MOF-74 and B,N-GQDs/NiFe-MOF-74. (e) OER polarization curves of B,N-GQDs/MOF-derived-NiFe-LDH in 1.0 M KOH solution.⁹⁴ (e) Synthesis procedure of NiFe-LDH electrocatalysts. (g) HRTEM images of Ni-MOFs-Fe after being soaked in 1.0 M KOH. (h) LSV polarization curves of N-1, F-1, NF-10, RuO₂ and carbon paper (CP). (i) Ni 2p and (j) Fe 2p XPS spectra of NF-10, N-1 and F-1 after being soaked in 1.0 M KOH.³⁹

4.3 MOF-derived metal@C

To maintain a large surface area and layered pore structure, and to increase the number of exposed active sites, several groups have attempted to *in situ* grow MOFs on templates, and then synthesize metal@C composites.⁹⁵ **Error! Reference source not**

found. Such MOFs-derived metal@C composites have been widely studied as high-performance electrocatalysts.⁹⁶⁻⁹⁹ However, the structural stability of metal@C is sacrificed due to the unstable interface between the MOF and the added heterogeneous components. As a novel strategy to overcome this limitation, Yun et al.¹⁰⁰ proposed selecting a Zn-MOF matched with a Co-MOF lattice as a template to construct a double-shell metal@C catalyst. First, the morphology of Zn-MOF was controlled by cationic surfactants, and then Co-MOF was grown on the surface of Zn-MOF with two morphologies. N-C-in-Co/N-C catalysts with nanorod- and rhombic dodecahedron-shaped hollow morphologies (NR-H-C and RD-H-C) were obtained using a simple pyrolysis technique (**Fig. 12a**). TEM images show that the catalyst presents a hollow structure (**Fig. 12b, d**). HRTEM shows two kinds of lattice fringes, which belong to graphite and Co nanoparticles respectively (**Fig. 12c, e**). This structure containing partially exposed Co nanoparticles coated with carbon layers helps expose the active sites, shortening the charge transfer distance, and promoting the overall water-splitting performance. The hierarchical porous structure of the catalyst facilitates mass transfer in electrochemical processes, and the high surface area ensures adequate contact between the active site and the electrolyte and exposes more active sites (**Fig. 12f, g, i**). As an alkaline HER electrode, NR-H-C showed better HER activity, with an overpotential of 123 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² (**Fig. 12h**). At the same time, all the samples showed improved stability comparable to commercial Pt/C (**Fig. 12j**). Overall, this work provided structural engineering design strategies for the construction of metal@C electrocatalysts showing remarkable performance and stability.

Figure 12. (a) Schematic illustration of the synthesis of NR-H-C and RD-H-C. (b) TEM image and (c) HRTEM images of NR-H-C. (d) TEM image and (e) HRTEM image of RD-H-C. (f,g) N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms of NR-H-C (f) and RD-H-C (g). (h) Polarization curves of NR-H-C, RD-H-C, rhombic dodecahedron Co/N-C (RD-C), Pt/C, and Ni foam. (i) CP durability test. (j) CP durability test.¹⁰⁰

MOF-derived metal@C electrocatalysts are usually prepared by pyrolysis for several hours in an inert atmosphere and at high temperatures around 600 ~ 900 °C, which is a time-consuming and energy-demanding process.^{101,102} To address this constraint, Bo et al.⁹⁶ proposed a laser scribing method for the preparation of MOF-derived Co nanoparticles/porous N-doped graphene (Co/PNG) under air atmosphere and room temperature. Upon conversion of the organic complex to PNG by laser engraving, the decomposition of the organic ligand produced a reducing chemical atmosphere that combined with the high energy of the local laser irradiation was able to reduce Co ions into metallic Co species, forming the Co/PNG. In addition, Co/PNG

supported by a flexible polyimide (PI) film was directly used as electrocatalytic electrodes without additional adhesives. The electrocatalytic activity of the obtained electrodes was optimized by adjusting the laser energy and the loading of MOFs. The electrocatalytic results showed that Co/PNG exhibited satisfactory activity and stability for water splitting. Due to its porous structure and the large number of Co-N_x active sites, Co/PNG exhibited 131, 335, and 380 mV overpotential in HER, OER, and overall water splitting at current densities of 10 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH solution. **Table 2** gives an exhaustive list of reported MOF-derived metal@C catalysts in recent years.

Table 2. Summary of some MOF-derived metal@C for water splitting activity

Electrocatalyst	Electrolyte	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Overpotential (mV)	Reference
Co/N-C	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 123	100
Co/PNG	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 131 OER 335	96
Fe-Co-CN/rGO	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 215 OER 308	103
Ni@NCS	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 366	104
	1.0 M KOH	10	OER 330	
N-HPCS@Co ₁ Cu ₁ Fe NSs	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 114	105
Co-NC	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 242	106
Ni@N-HCGHF	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 95 OER 260	107
Co-N-C	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 75 OER 370	108
Co@NC/CNT	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 137 OER 302	109
Co@NCNTs	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 280	110
	1.0 M KOH		HER 240	
Co/Ni@GC/NCNTs/CNFs	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 150	111

			OER 395	
FeNi/PNG	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 132	112
			OER 353	
CoNi@NCNTs	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 130	113
	0.1 M KOH		OER 370	

4.4 MOF-derived metal phosphides

Transition metal phosphides (TMPs), like other transition metal compounds such as carbides, chalcogenides, nitrides, etc., are characterized by considerable electrical conductivity and stability.¹¹⁴⁻¹¹⁶ Moreover, P atoms in TMPs reduce the binding energy between the transition metal and hydrogen, so the ΔG_{H^*} of most TMPs tends to zero.¹¹⁷ The negatively charged P atom in TMP is able to capture positively charged protons in the HER process due to its high electronegativity,¹¹⁸ thus exhibiting higher intrinsic catalytic activity, with low overpotentials and Tafel slopes in a wide pH range. On top of this, TMPs show exceptional stabilities under electrolysis conditions.¹¹⁹

Based on the combined design of composition and geometric structure, Lei et al.¹²⁰ prepared 3D NiCoP nanoleaves arrays on Ni foam (NiCoP@NF) by a simple hydrothermal and phosphating two-step method using the Ni foam both as support and Ni source. The use of the Ni foam substrate not only improved the electrical conductivity of the catalyst but also avoided the use of additional adhesives, which reduced the contact resistance between the catalyst and substrate, and improved the ion diffusion and electron transfer rate. Actually, 3D Ni foams have been widely used as support material in electrocatalytic water splitting as they can provide high current density and good durability.^{121,122} Moreover, in NiCoP@NF, the vertical growth of the layered nanosheets endowed the catalyst with abundant active sites, which facilitated the gas release (**Fig. 13a**). As shown in **Fig. 13b, c**, NiCoP@NF required overpotentials of just 98 and 87 mV to provide a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² for HER in alkaline and acidic electrolytes, respectively.

The mass/charge transfer capacity of an electrocatalyst in the reaction process,

which is mainly determined by its SSA and porous structure, has a great influence on its performance.¹²³ Compared with common disordered micropores or mesoporous structures, 3D-ordered macropores can not only promote electrolyte penetration in the catalyst, but also shorten the electron/ion diffusion path, and ensure that the reactants and intermediates interact with the internal active sites.¹²⁴ Recently, by carbonization and phosphatization of the polystyrene sphere-template ZIF-67 assembly, Wu et al.¹²⁵ designed a composite electrocatalyst composed of highly dispersed Co/CoP heterojunctions embedded in a hierarchical ordered microporous-mesoporous-microporous carbon matrix (Co/CoP@HOMC, **Fig. 13d**). The combined experimental and theoretical results showed that the Co/CoP heterojunction interface not only provided a large number of exposed active centers but also optimized the hydrogen/water adsorption free energy through electronic coupling, while the interconnected macroporous structure facilitated the accessibility to all the active centers with superior proton transfer capabilities (**Fig. 13e, f**). The experimental results showed that the as-prepared Co/CoP@HOMC composite exhibited excellent catalytic activities for HER and OER in 1.0 M KOH, with overpotentials of only 120 mV and 260 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², respectively. In addition, Co/CoP@HOMC was superior to Pt@C||IrO₂@C in an alkaline electrolyzer (**Fig. 13g-i**).

The above two research works focused on the optimization of the architecture of the TMP catalyst, accelerating the mass and charge transfer process, improving the electrical conductivity, or using interface engineering to improve the adsorption energy of the relevant species at the active sites. Several other TMPs have received extensive attention and research as HER electrocatalysts in the past few years. The electrocatalytic properties of some MOF-derived TMPs are summarized in **Table 3**.

Figure 13. (a) SEM images at different magnifications of NiCoP@NF-100. (b,c) Electrocatalytic performance of different catalysts in 1.0 M KOH (b), and 0.5 M H₂SO₄ (c);¹²⁰ (d) Schematic illustration of the synthetic process. (e) TEM images of Co/CoP@HOMC. (f) Aberration-corrected High angle annular dark-field (HAADF) image of the Co/CoP@HOMC. (g) LSV curves of HER. (h) LSV curves of OER. (i) Polarization curves of the Co/CoP@HOMC||Co/CoP@HOMC and Pt@C||IrO₂@C for overall water splitting.¹²⁵

Table 3. Summary of some MOF-derived metal phosphides electrocatalysts for water splitting.

Electrocatalyst	Electrolyte	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Overpotential (mV)	Reference
NiCoP@NF-100	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 87	120
	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 98	

Co/CoP@HOMC	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 120	125
			OER 260	
CoP-NC@NFP	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 162	126
			OER 270	
CCS-NiFeP	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 56	127
			OER 201	
Cu ₃ P@C	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 124	128
FeNiP/PG	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 173	129
		10	OER 292	
NiCoP Nanoflakes	1.0 M KOH	100	HER 199	130
		500	HER 283	
		1000	HER 317	
		100	OER 315	130
		500	OER 378	
		1000	OER 416	
NF@Fe ₂ -Ni ₂ P/C	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 39	131
			OER 205	
Co ₄ Ni ₁ P NTs	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 129	132
			OER 245	
FeCoNiP@NC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 93	133
	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 187	
	1.0 M KOH	10	OER 266	
NiCoP/NF	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 78	134
			OER 262	
CoFeP TPAs/Ni	1.0 M KOH	10	HER 43	135
		100	HER 113	
		900	HER 263	
		10	OER 198	
		100	OER 250	

		700	OER 335	
NiCoP-BDC/NF	1.0 M KOH	50	HER 170	136
		50	OER 323	

4.5 MOF-derived metal sulfides

Some transition metal sulfides (TMSs) are also excellent candidate HER catalysts with relatively low cost and high activity. Among them, layered MoS₂ has attracted particular attention, but its serious aggregation and poor intrinsic conductivity restrict its potential electrocatalytic activity.¹³⁷ Numerous previous studies have shown that the edge position of MoS₂ is the active site for HER. Thus, designing and engineering layered MoS₂ electrocatalysts with tuned and stable architectures is one of the approaches that has been used to enhance HER activity.^{138,139} The existing methods for preparing MoS₂ with few layers are complex and harmful to the environment. In view of this, Tang et al.¹⁴⁰ designed a one-pot general method for the synthesis of a few layers of MoS₂/nitrogen and sulfur co-doped porous carbon (MoS₂/NSPC) electrocatalyst (**Fig. 14a**). The structure with few layers of MoS₂ embedded in N, S-doped carbon can provide a special microenvironment and conductive channel to promote electron and ion transport in HER process (**Fig. 14b, c**). In 0.5 M H₂SO₄, the obtained overpotential at 10 mA cm⁻² was 114 mV (**Fig. 14d**). In addition, using the same strategy, WS₂/NSPC was also produced, demonstrating the generality of the method. Besides WS₂/NSPC also demonstrated notable HER activity (**Fig. 14e, f**).

Figure 14. (a) Illustration of the synthesis and the structure of few-layered MoS₂/NSPC. (b) TEM and (c) HRTEM of the optimal sample MoS₂/NSPC-0.075. (d) Polarization curves (iR corrected) for HER in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. (e) HRTEM image of WS₂/NSPC. (f) Polarization curves (iR corrected) for HER in 0.5 M H₂SO₄.¹⁴⁰

Due to synergies, interface defects, and stratification, the complexes of two or more TMSs show improvements in conductivity, SSA, and active site density, compared to single-component TMSs in water splitting.¹⁴¹⁻¹⁴³ Inspired by this, Huang's group¹⁴⁴ proposed a low-temperature molten salt synthesis method to prepare an efficient MoS₂/CoS₂ heterojunction catalyst for HER in one step, employing potassium thiocyanate (KSCN) as the sulfur source (Fig. 15a). TEM images confirmed the formation of MoS₂@CoS₂ heterostructures (Fig. 15b). Since the heterojunction changes the electronic structure of the material, the ΔG_{H^*} value shows that the MoS₂@CoS₂ heterojunction has better ΔG_{H^*} , which is conducive to the smooth hydrogen adsorption/desorption reaction in electrolytic water. HER test results showed an overpotential of 96 mV was required to reach a current density of 10 mA cm⁻², with a Tafel slope of 60 mV dec⁻¹ in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ (Fig. 15c-e). Electrochemical tests confirmed that the HER catalytic activity of the MoS₂@CoS₂ heterojunction was

significantly higher than that of MoS₂ and CoS₂ materials.

Du et al.¹⁴⁵ prepared ZnS@Co₉S₈@Ni₃S₂ nanoarrays (ZCNS) using thioacetamide (TAA) as the sulfur source by a two-step hydrothermal method (**Fig. 15f**). HRTEM characterization showed that the three phases, ZnS, Co₉S₈, and Ni₃S₂, co-existed and there were obvious heterogeneous interfaces (**Fig. 15g**). Electrochemical tests showed that ZCNS-1/2 requires an overpotential of 97 mV to achieve a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² for HER (**Fig. 15h**). The heterostructure realized the combination of larger ΔG_{H₂O} of Ni₃S₂ and good metal activity of Co₉S₈, which greatly improved the overall catalytic performance of ZCNS-1/2 (**Fig. 15i, j**). A list of recently studied MOF-derived TMSs electrocatalysts is provided in **Table 4**.

Figure 15. (a) Schematic of the preparation of MoS₂@CoS₂. (b) HRTEM images of MoS₂@CoS₂. (c) Polarization curves and (d) Tafel plots of the samples. (e) Calculated ΔG_{H*} of the three models;¹⁴⁴

(f) Synthetic steps of the MOF-derived hollow ZCNS-1/2 nanosword arrays (NSAs). (g) TEM images of a single NS from ZCNS-1/2. (h) *iR*-corrected LSV curves. (i) Chemisorption free energies of H₂O and (j) density of states for ZnS, Co₉S₈ and Ni₃S₂.¹⁴⁵

Table 4. Summary of some MOF-derived TMSs for water-splitting activity

Electrocatalyst	Electrolyte	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	Overpotential (mV)	Reference
MoS ₂ @CoS ₂	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 96	¹⁴⁴ Error!
				Reference
				source
				not
				found.
MoS ₂ /NSPC	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 114	140
CoS ₂ /FeS-MOF@NF	1 M KOH	10	OER 136	146
CoS ₂ -MoS ₂ HNAs/Ti	1 M KOH	10	HER 82	147
		10	OER 266	
Fe-NiS/MoS ₂	1 M KOH	10	HER 120	148
			OER 290	
FeS ₂ -MoS ₂ @CoS ₂ -MOF	1 M KOH	10	HER 92	149
		50	HER 152	
		100	HER 183	
	1 M KOH	20	OER 211	149
		50	OER 244	
		100	OER 280	
Co ₉ S ₈ /CoS _{1.097} /rGO	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 188	150
Co/CoS/Fe-HSNC	1 M KOH	10	HER 138	151
			OER 250	
CoS _{1.097}	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	10	HER 163	152
NiS/CoNC	1 M KOH	10	OER 46	153
Ni-BDC@NiS	1 M KOH	20	OER 330	154

NiS/MoS ₂ /C	1 M KOH	10	HER 117	155
CoS ₂ @NiS-MoS ₂	1 M KOH	10	HER 91	156

4.6 MOF-derived metal carbides

Transition metal carbides (TMCs) have attracted extensive attention due to their excellent intrinsic characteristics and performance, including high electrical conductivity and an appropriate density of states (DOS) near the Fermi level.^{157,158} For example, tungsten carbide-based electrocatalysts exhibit excellent HER activity because of their “Pt-like” electronic structure.^{159,160} Although metal carbide-based catalysts have been widely reported and show great application prospects, it is still challenging to engineer TMC catalysts with controllable nanostructures and long-term durability. In this direction, Gong et al.¹⁶¹ demonstrated the *in situ* growth of Mo-MOF on nickel foam by converting predeposited bimetallic hydroxide/oxide nanosheets (**Fig. 16a**). After pyrolysis, ultrafine molybdenum carbide nanoparticles wrapped in Co and nitrogen-doped carbon layers were obtained (Mo_xCo_yC/NF) (**Fig. 16b**). While the ultrafine nanoparticles increase exposure to active sites, the *in situ* growth enhances bonding between catalyst and substrate, and cobalt and nitrogen-doped carbon layers promote charge transfer and catalytic stability. Overall, at the current density of 10 mA cm⁻² in alkaline solution, an overpotential of only 33.5 mV and excellent stability (> 60 h) were demonstrated for HER (**Fig. 16c, d**).

During high-temperature synthesis, Mo₂C will inevitably agglomerate, losing part of the surface active sites.^{162,163} This loss can be prevented through morphological modulation of the material.^{164,165} In this direction, Wang et al.¹⁶⁶ reported a new method based on MOFs for the preparation of heterogeneous electrocatalysts (**Fig. 16e, g**). Unlike conventional MOF-derived composites, the Mo₂C nanosheets were vertically arranged on the surface of a cobalt-embedded N-doped carbon polyhedron (Mo₂C/Co@NC) (**Fig. 16f**). **Fig. 16h** shows the transfer of electrons from Co to Mo₂C through their interface. Due to the interpenetration and the strong interfacial coupling effect between Mo₂C nanosheets and Co@NC polyhedra, the hydrogen adsorption free

energy of the catalyst is further optimized (**Fig. 16i**), and the intrinsic activity of $\text{Mo}_2\text{C}/\text{Co@NC}$ is significantly improved.

Figure 16. (a) Schematic illustration of the synthesis of $\text{CoMo-MOF}/\text{NF}$. (b) HRTEM images of $\text{Mo}_x\text{Co}_y\text{C}/\text{NF}$. (c) LSV curves $\text{Mo}_x\text{Co}_y\text{C}/\text{NF}$, $\text{W}_x\text{Co}_y\text{C}/\text{NF}$, $\text{Co}_x\text{C}/\text{NF}$, and $\text{Pt}/\text{C}/\text{NF}$. (d) The long-term HER stability test of $\text{Mo}_x\text{Co}_y\text{C}/\text{NF}$ at the current densities of 20 mA cm^{-2} and 100 mA cm^{-2} .¹⁶¹ (e) Schematic illustration for the synthesis of $\text{Mo}_2\text{C}/\text{Co@NC}$. (f) TEM images for $\text{Mo}_2\text{C}/\text{Co@NC}$. (g) XRD patterns. (h) High-resolution Co 2p XPS spectrum. (i) Free energy diagram of HER on Mo_2C (101) and $\text{Mo}_2\text{C}/\text{Co@NC}$.¹⁶⁶

4.7 MOF-derived metal nitrides

The essence of transition metal nitrides (TMNs) is that heteroatomic nitrogen is

embedded in the lattice of the main metal. That is, TMNs are a kind of interstitial compound¹⁶⁷. TMNs are widely used in electrocatalysis because of their metallic behavior, excellent electrical conductivity, and effective oxygen adsorption.^{168,169} Because most metals or metal oxides usually have very high melting points, the method of direct ammoniation under NH₃ atmosphere to prepare TMNs requires high pressure conditions.¹⁷⁰ However, the high cost of high pressure reactions hampers mass production. To get around this restriction, Fu et al.¹⁷¹ adopted the “MOFs plus MOFs” strategy to combine early-transition metal nitrides (e.g. Mo₂N) and late-transition metals (e.g. Co, **Fig. 17a**), and obtained hollow Co-Mo₂N tubes (S-2-T5) with a Co outer layer on an inner core of Mo₂N (**Fig. 17b, c**). The catalyst can be further optimized by adjusting the Co/Mo ratio in the precursor. The results showed that the combination of Co and Mo₂N can significantly improve the catalytic activity in an alkaline solution. Using this material, overpotentials of only 76 mV, 302 mV, and 346 mV were needed to achieve a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² for HER, OER, and overall water splitting (**Fig. 17d-f**). In this material, the close contact between Co and Mo₂N allows the optimization of the adsorption of reactants, the good conductivity of Mo₂N is advantageous to charge transfer/transport, and the tubular structure facilitates mass transfer.

Preparing TMNs using MOFs as a precursor system usually requires high temperature carbonization, which causes metal agglomeration and reduces exposure of the active sites.¹⁷² At the same time, the limited types and quantities of heteroatoms in the MOF backbone prevent significant enhancement of the final catalyst performance. Taking these factors into account, Zou et al.¹⁷³ used MOF-based dry xerogels (MOFXs) and additional heteroatomic precursors to achieve higher levels of doping and defects in the carbon framework, as well as highly dispersed ultra-small Fe₂N NPs (**Fig. 17g**). From the HRTEM image, it can be observed that Fe₂N particles are scattered in the carbon sheet (**Fig. 17h**). The double doping of N and S improves the electronic structure of carbon, provides more active sites, and promotes the catalytic performance together with Fe₂N, which was confirmed by the DFT (**Fig. 17i**).

Figure 17. (a) Schematic representation of the synthesis, (b) TEM images, (c) HRTEM images, (d) HER LSV curves, (e) OER LSV curves, and (f) overall water splitting LSV curve in 1.0 M KOH of a Co-Mo₂N hybrid.¹⁷¹ (g) Schematic illustration of catalyst derivation, (h) HRTEM micrograph, and (i) calculated HER free energies.¹⁷³

4.8 MOF-derived metal oxides

Transition metal oxides (TMOs) are widely used OER catalysts providing high catalytic activity and stability. Their OER performance is closely related to their electronic structure.^{174,175} However, for a long time, it was extensively considered that pure metal oxides were not good HER catalysts because the H-O bond formed by the proton and the oxygen atom of the oxide during the reaction was too strong, preventing hydrogen desorption.¹⁷⁶ Despite this, some oxides have recently shown high HER performance.¹⁷⁷ For example, Maji et al.¹⁷⁸ synthesized core-shell electrocatalyst Co₃O₄@Co/NCNT (NCNT = nitrogen-doped carbon nanotubes) by two-step calcination using Co-MOF as precursor (**Fig. 18a**). The core-shell structure of the composite material can be seen in the TEM image of Co₃O₄@Co/NCNT (**Fig. 18b**).

The Co₃O₄@Co/NCNT achieved current densities of 10 mA cm⁻² at an overpotential of 171 mV in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ for HER (**Fig. 18c**). Theoretical calculation showed that the N-center of Co-N₄ is the active site of H⁺ binding (**Fig. 18d, e**).

The carbonized derivatives obtained from MOFs can perfectly combine metal oxides with carbon materials and thus are considered excellent precursors for the construction of efficient electrocatalysts.^{179,180} However, traditional synthesis methods (hydro/solvothermal,^{181,182} coprecipitation,^{183,184} microwave-assisted,^{24,185} etc.) generally produce MOFs in powder form, thus presenting serious agglomeration problems after the carbonization process. Overcoming this limitation is a topic of major interest. Recently, Lu et al.¹⁸⁶ reported a polyaniline-assisted one-step pyrolysis of bimetallic MOFs to synthesize NF@NC-CoFe₂O₄/C nanorod arrays. First, a layer of polyaniline was deposited on the surface of Ni foam by electrochemical deposition, and then MOF-74-Co/Fe nanorod arrays were grown on the surface by hydrothermal method. Finally, porous CoFe₂O₄/C composite nanorod arrays were obtained by one-step pyrolysis in N₂ atmosphere, which avoided the consumption of carbon materials and structural damage during secondary air treatment (**Fig. 18f**). Polyaniline deposited on the surface of Ni foam played an important role in trapping transition metal ions and inducing crystal growth orientation. CoFe₂O₄/C nanorod arrays (CoFe₂O₄/C), where the CoFe₂O₄ was coated with an amorphous carbon layer, were obtained by this pyrolysis method (**Fig. 18g**). This structure not only improves the overall conductivity but also inhibits the agglomeration of the catalyst during long-term operation. Some reported representative MOF-derived metal oxide electrocatalysts are shown in **Table 5**.

Figure 18. (a) Schematic showing the carbonization and calcination leading to the formation of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{Co}/\text{NCNT}$. (b) TEM image of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{Co}$ core-shell encapsulated in NCNT. (c) LSV showing HER activity of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{Co}/\text{NCNT}$. (d,e) Free energy plots of H-adsorption on N-center (d) and Co-center of all the considered systems (e).¹⁷⁸ (f) Schematic illustration of the one-step PANI-assisted synthesis of a bimetal-organic framework NRAs and its derived porous $\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{C}$ nanorod arrays (NRAs). (g) HRTEM image of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles encapsulated by carbon layers.¹⁸⁶

Table 5. Summary of some MOF-derived metal oxides for water splitting activity

Electrocatalyst	Electrolyte	Current density (mA cm^{-2})	Overpotential (mV)	Reference
$\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4@\text{Co}/\text{NCNT}$	0.5 M H_2SO_4	10	HER 171	178
$\text{NF}@\text{NC-CoFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{C}$ NRAs	1 M KOH	10	OER 220	186
$\text{NiO}/\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4$	1 M KOH	10	HER 169.5	187
			OER 270	
$\text{NiFe}_2\text{O}_4@\text{N}/\text{rGO}$	1 M KOH	10	HER 157	188
		20	OER 252	

CoNi-CoO-NiO@NC	1 M KOH	10	OER 352	189
NiO WCP/CP	1 M KOH	10	OER 393	190
Ni/NiO/C	1 M KOH	10	HER 123	191
NiO hollow spheres	1 M KOH	10	OER 323	192
Fe-Co-O/Co@NC-mNS/NF	1 M KOH	10	HER 112	193
			OER 257	
HP-Co ₃ O ₄ @200 arrays/NF	1 M KOH	10	OER 205	194
Co ₃ O ₄ @Z67-N700@CeO ₂	0.1 M KOH	10	OER 350	195
M-Co ₃ O ₄	1 M KOH	10	OER 370	196

5. Summary and outlook

In this review, the recent advances of MOFs and their derivatives in the framework of electrocatalytic water splitting were reviewed, with special emphasis on describing the used synthesis methods, the obtained architecture, the material's catalytic performance, and the mechanisms allowing their production and providing them with improved catalytic activity and stability. MOFs exhibit several advantages over conventional catalysts associated with their unique architecture and physicochemical properties. First, the large surface area of MOFs facilitates more active sites to be exposed to the electrolyte. In addition, the porous structure of MOFs facilitates both electron and proton transport. Second, by adjusting the types of ligands and metal centers, MOFs with a wide range of geometries, architectures, compositions, electronic properties, and chemical environments can be constructed under different preparation conditions, providing numerous degrees of freedom to optimize their catalytic performance. Third, MOFs are suitable precursors/templates for preparing a vast array of derivatives, such as MOF-derived metal@carbon, metal oxides, phosphides, sulfides, nitrides, and carbides. These derivatives can potentially inherit the original microstructures of MOFs while showing improved electrical conductivity and chemical stability. In addition, the ligands containing heteroatoms can incorporate N, S, or P atoms into the carbon matrix after transformation to regulate the coordination

microenvironment of the active center and its electronic structure. However, in practical application, electrocatalysts based on MOFs and their derivatives still show particularly prominent shortcomings: (i) While MOFs generally show poor conductivity, site accessibility, and stability, when producing their derivatives part of the porosity and surface area, and especially the excellent level of control over MOF parameters is lost. (ii) No unified understanding of the catalytic mechanism of MOF-based electrocatalysts is available due to their notable structural and compositional complexity, which prevents the rational optimization of their catalytic performance. Thus, further efforts are needed to develop cost-effective catalysts with better catalytic properties and understand their catalytic mechanisms. The following are some of the current challenges and future opportunities and prospects in this area (**Fig. 19**).

(1) MOF-based electrocatalysts. Due to their adjustable surface area and pore structure, as well as their wide variety of compositions and metal centers, MOFs are considered excellent candidate electrocatalysts for water splitting. However, due to the insulating character of the organic ligands and the poor conjugation properties of metal-organic connections, MOFs have poor intrinsic conductivity which limits their electrocatalytic activity. Thus, it is urgent to develop higher electrical conductivity MOFs to be directly used as electrocatalytic materials. The charge transport in MOFs depends on the degree of orbital space and energy overlap, so enhancing orbital overlap can effectively improve the carrier migration capacity of MOFs. The combination of ultrathin (2D) MOF layers with CNTs, carbon nanosheets, graphene, and other conductive carbon materials in the synthesis process is an alternative strategy to improve the conductivity of MOF-based electrodes. On the other hand, the pore size of most bulk MOFs is too small, which makes proton transfer slow and affects the charge transfer process. To overcome this limitation, again ultrathin layers of 2D MOFs may be required. Compared with bulk MOFs, the smaller thickness of 2D MOFs can shorten the electron/ion transport distance and improve the reaction rate. For 2D MOFs, the catalytic activity of HER can be improved by changing the type of active metal centers, adjusting the electronic structure of metal sites, and increasing the electron density. In

addition, by adjusting the ligand and the synthesis method, the preparation of macroporous/microporous MOFs can facilitate the migration of reactants and the escape of bubbles.

Another limitation of current MOFs is their moderate mechanical strength and poor chemical stability, which is associated with the moderate strength of the chemical bond between the metal ions and multi-toothed organic ligands. To overcome this drawback, researchers have developed a variety of modification strategies, such as building stronger coordination bonds,¹⁹⁷ enhancing the connectivity of construction units,¹⁹⁸ increasing the hydrophobicity of MOFs,¹⁹⁹ and so on. However, how to further improve the chemical stability without changing other advantages remains challenging. In addition, considering the excellent chemical stability of covalent organic framework (COF) materials, the researchers prepared metal-covalent organic frameworks (MCOFs), which combine the high porosity, high SSA, and excellent chemical stability of both.²⁰⁰

At present, most reported MOF-based catalysts are usually powder materials, which need to be mixed with binders when preparing working electrodes for electrocatalytic tests, resulting in a large number of gaps and additives between powder catalysts and substrates that may hinder the electron/proton transfer of the catalyst and increase the resistance of the catalyst, resulting in poor electrocatalytic activity. To go around these constraints, self-supported structures involving the vertical growth of 2D MOF nanosheets on conductive substrates, such as CC and metal conductive substrates can be used. These structures can be also subsequently processed into various MOF-derived 2D nanosheet arrays without a dramatic change in the overall material architecture. The self-supported electrode has the advantages of good electronic conductivity, no binder, and open space nanoarray that can expose more active sites. Besides, conductive substrates provide good mechanical properties and directly grown materials typically show improved interphases and stability against peeling-off, so they have better prospects for industrial application.

(2) MOF-derived electrocatalysts. MOFs, with adjustable metal ions and organic

ligands, are excellent building blocks of hybrid organic-inorganic composite catalysts. Besides, MOFs have proved to be very useful as templates for a variety of nanomaterials with unique micro- and nanostructures with adjusted composition. The derivatives obtained by pyrolysis can inherit the original structural characteristics of MOFs, with uniformly dispersed catalytic sites and high surface areas. In addition, the formed carbon layer can not only effectively improve the conductivity of the catalyst, but also protect the internal metal core, and improve the stability of the catalytic center. At the same time, the *in situ* doping of heteroatoms into the carbon matrix can adjust its electronic structure. Therefore, MOF-derived catalysts usually exhibit excellent electrocatalytic performance. However, MOF-derived metal@carbon materials are usually calcined at high temperatures under an inert gas atmosphere. The structural collapse and shrinkage of MOFs during pyrolysis, calcination, phosphating, vulcanization, and other post-treatment processes often lead to a sharp decline in their surface area and pore volume. The high-temperature sintering process also usually leads to metal agglomeration and decreases the number of exposed metal active sites, which adversely affects the corresponding catalytic activity. Therefore, it makes sense to replace this energy-intensive process with milder conditions for large-scale applications. As an example, using hard templates, such as eutectic salt or silicon oxide, can effectively reduce the collapse of the pore structure of the precursor, and can also form a large pore structure to provide rapid proton transfer. Designing suitable synthesis strategies for MOF-derived small-sized clusters or single-atom catalysts is one of the new hot topics in the field of electrocatalysis particularly electrocatalytic water splitting.

(3) *In situ* characterization techniques and theoretical calculations. The influence of the evolution of the catalyst composition and internal structure on performance during a long-term working process can not be ignored. Besides, to develop highly active and stable catalytic materials for water splitting, it is very important to have a thorough understanding of the reaction mechanism and intermediate process. *In situ* characterization techniques, including *in situ* XRD, TEM, XAS, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, XPS, Raman, electron paramagnetic resonance, etc. can be used

to reveal the catalytic mechanism and structural changes. Such *in situ* characterization techniques can monitor the change of the geometric and electronic structure of the catalyst in the catalytic process in real-time, to conduct a clearer and more comprehensive study of the catalyst in the real catalytic reaction environment. Besides, these measurements can accurately identify the dynamic chemical properties of real active sites and reaction intermediates, reveal the catalytic mechanism, explore the synergistic effect, and provide guidance for the accurate design of highly active sites. Such *in situ* characterization techniques for HER and OER on such complex catalysts as MOFs and MOF-derivatives need to be further developed.

Besides, such experimental analyses need to be combined with theoretical calculation, to reveal the reaction mechanism of the active center of the catalyst, and provide theoretical guidance for regulating and optimizing the composition, configuration, electronic structure, and coordination environment of the catalyst. However, currently, there is a too strong reliance on the adsorption results of the “model” surface defined by the DFT calculation, which itself has a certain uncertainty in terms of functional selection. To avoid such problems, it is again necessary to conduct strict characterization of the surface to ensure that the electrode surface will not be reconstructed during the electrolysis process and maintain the assumed state.

(4) Industrial mass production of catalysts. Towards industrialization, two key issues of catalyst should be solved: (i) the cost of raw materials, energy usage, consumables, and production equipment need to be minimized and the reaction yields need to be maximized to reduce the overall cost; (ii) high throughput MOF and MOF derivative synthesis methods suitable for mass production need to be developed. In addition, the long-term stability at high current density, especially under strong alkaline and acidic conditions, is a fundamental parameter to measure the catalyst viability for real applications. Therefore, it is necessary to systematically study the synthesis principle of MOFs with chemical and mechanical stability. The reproducibility and precision of electrode synthesis to target products is one of the biggest challenges in mass production and requires further clarification. To obtain the desired product more

accurately, it is necessary to study and understand the synthesis method and working mechanism more specifically. While noble metals are still the first choice for commercial catalysts, it is necessary to develop and explore naturally abundant catalysts with competing performance and lower costs in the long run.

Figure 19. Development prospect and challenges of MOF materials for water electrolysis.

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